

Common Infrastructure for National Cohorts in Europe, Canada, and Africa - CINECA -

Deliverable D1.4

Data interoperability documentation

Work Package:	WP1 - Federated Data Discovery and Querying
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Contractual Delivery Date:	30th June 2023
Actual Delivery Date:	30th June 2023
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Dissemination Level:	Public
Type of Deliverable:	Report
Grant agreement:	No. 825775 Horizon 2020 (H2020-SC1-BHC-2018-2020)
Type of action:	RIA
Start Date:	1 Jan 2019
Duration:	54 months

Table of contents:

1. Executive Summary	3
2. Project objectives	3
3. Detailed report on the deliverable	3
3.1 Background	3
3.2 Standards	4
3.2.1 Beacon	4
3.2.2 Phenopackets	4
3.2.3 Passport	5
3.2.4 Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure	5
3.2.5 Data Use Ontology	5
3.2.6 Htsget	5
3.2.7 Crypt4GH	6
3.2.8 File Formats	6
3.2.9 Task Execution Service	6
3.3 Description of Work	6
3.3.1 Beacon Reference Implementation	6
3.3.2 Beacon Network	7
3.3.3 WP4 Use case	7
3.3.4 WP5 Use Case	8
3.4 Next steps	8
4. References	9
Standards	9
Implementations	9
5. Abbreviations	9
6. Delivery and schedule	10
7. Adjustments made	10
8. Appendices	10
Appendix 1	10
Appendix 2	11

1. Executive Summary

This document describes the standards utilised, and the implementations and deployments of these standards during the CINECA project. It links to the documentation of the standards, as well as the implementations and deployments supporting the discovery, access control, and metadata required to enable the use cases to perform their respective federated analyses. The document links to other projects, such as the European Genomic Data Infrastructure and H2020 projects which utilise and will extend the work and standards described in this document.

2. Project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the following objectives:

- a) Provide links to all documentation on the standards and implementations used to support federated data discovery and analysis
- b) Describe deployments of applications of these standards, and how they support examples from the use cases (WPs 4 & 5)
- c) Link the work in CINECA to other projects, such as the Genomic Data Infrastructure, Federated EGA, or European Joint Programme on Rare Disease.

3. Detailed report on the deliverable

3.1 Background

Enabling federated data discovery, data access, and research and analysis, by implementing the same standards across the federated network, is crucial in order to permit the same or similar analyses to be performed across the different cohorts. As CINECA¹ aims to support trans-continental federated analysis across cohorts located in Canada, Africa and Europe, choosing these standards is critical to the success of the project. The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health² (GA4GH) is a standards setting organisation that aims to facilitate research in genomic and healthcare data. Some of the standards being developed by GA4GH, and their use in CINECA, are described here. GA4GH is comprised of driver projects³ and work streams⁴. The driver projects have a specific set of use-cases for one or more standards, and the work streams are there to develop the standards required for the driver projects use-cases. To enable interoperability between the cohorts, and hence the analysis and discovery processes within CINECA, GA4GH standards were chosen as the basis for these implementations.

There are 2 main types of work streams within GA4GH, foundational work streams and technical work streams. The foundational work streams - Data Security, and Regulatory and Ethics - comprise core issues that relate to all GA4GH work, and as such provide guidance to both driver projects and

¹ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/>

² <https://www.ga4gh.org/>

³ <https://www.ga4gh.org/how-we-work/driver-projects/>

⁴ <https://www.ga4gh.org/how-we-work/workstreams/>

technical workstreams. The technical work streams develop and extend the technical standards that are required by the driver projects. The technical work streams include the Clinical and Phenotypic Data Capture, the Cloud, the Data Use and Researcher Identity, the Discovery, the Genomic Knowledge Standards, and the Large Scale Genomics work streams. The standards developed by the technical work streams must be reviewed by both the foundational workstreams and a specially convened product review committee, before finally being approved by the GA4GH steering committee⁵.

3.2 Standards

Many of the standards that have been developed by the GA4GH are already in use within CINECA or associated cohorts; below is a brief overview of some of those applicable standards, and how they facilitate CINECA processes with links to the documentation detailing the standard, while [Appendix 2](#) contains a table which references the specification of the standard, as well as the documentation of the standard.

3.2.1 Beacon

The Beacon⁶ standard is a GA4GH standard that was originally designed to support queries on alleles (gene variants) but aims to protect the identity of the participants by returning a response based on the existence of an allele within a cohort, which was boolean or count dependent on the user's access level. This allowed users to perform discovery queries without having access to the data a priori. The standard was updated to version 2 with input from CINECA WP1, which allows record level queries, as well as queries on phenotype and assay as well as extended variant queries, while maintaining the restrictions of the original standard if necessary. For example, registered users include those with 'bona-fide'⁷ status within the LifeScience AAI (see Passports section below), could access more information than anonymous users, depending on the settings of the individual beacon. The extension of the beacon standard also meant that the network implementation, which allows a network of beacons to be queried using a single query, needed to be updated as well.

3.2.2 Phenopackets

Transferring phenotypic data between different resources in a standardised way is a requirement to ensure that both phenotypic queries and data transfer are consistent across a federated network. Phenopackets⁸ provide the information model that different levels of clinical and phenotypic data require in order to be exchanged. Phenopackets are a GA4GH standard, and also an ISO standard⁹ for the exchange of phenotypic data. One of the benefits of the use of standards is evidenced by the loading of phenotypic data into a deployment of the Beacon reference implementation, the use of a standardised representation means the same loading and annotation pipeline can be used.

⁵ <https://www.ga4gh.org/how-we-work/ga4gh-product-approval/>

⁶ <https://github.com/ga4gh-beacon/specification>

⁷ <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41431-018-0219-y>

⁸ <https://github.com/phenopackets/phenopacket-schema>

⁹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/79991.html>

3.2.3 Passport

The Passport¹⁰ defines a standard way to represent the role and access rights of a particular user. It can be used to indicate if a particular user can access registered access resources, such as the Beacon, using the 'bona-fide' researcher attribute as implemented by ELIXIR¹¹. It also details which datasets the user has full controlled access to (via Controlled Access Visas), their affiliation(s), and their roles. However within a federated infrastructure, the LinkedIdentities visa facilitates the linking of institutional identities to the Passport, and hence LifeScience identity allowing a user to log into multiple different resources using a single, institutional, identity.

3.2.4 Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure

For Passports to work, there must be a standard for the infrastructure that details how to define the user's identity, and how to pass this information between federated cohorts in a consistent way. The GA4GH approved Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) OpenID Connect (OIDC) profile¹² for this purpose, which leverages the existing OpenID Connect (OIDC) standard to ensure maximum compatibility with existing identities.

3.2.5 Data Use Ontology

There are a diverse range of conditions which different cohorts apply to restrict use of their data. These can range from geographical restrictions, to restricting research for particular purposes, to requiring results to be published. To standardise the way these different requirements were communicated, the Data Use Ontology¹³ (DUO) was developed. This ensures that equivalent data use conditions are expressed in the same way across different cohorts. This is especially important when the cohorts are based in different legal jurisdictions, as they are with CINECA. The DUO also facilitates data discovery, for example via Beacon so when a researcher is investigating heart disease, the DUO can be used to ensure that only datasets that can be used for research into heart disease are returned as possible cohorts of interest.

3.2.6 Htsget

Htsget¹⁴ is a data streaming specification to allow the secure transfer of genomic data between locations. The standard supports range queries, for example allowing the user to just stream the gene of interest from a whole genome CRAM or BAM file, instead of downloading the whole file.

¹⁰ https://github.com/ga4gh-duri/ga4gh-duri.github.io/blob/master/researcher_ids/ga4gh_passport_v1.md

¹¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/services/compute/aai/bonafide>

¹² <https://ga4gh.github.io/data-security/aai-openid-connect-profile>

¹³ <https://github.com/EBISPOT/DUO>

¹⁴ <http://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/htsget.html>

3.2.7 Crypt4GH

Genomic data contains sensitive data on individuals, and as such preventing accidental disclosure of these data is extremely important. Crypt4GH¹⁵ is a file format that stores such data in an encrypted state. It supports fast decryption of the data, and also indexing allows random access of the files without having to decrypt the whole file. Such advantages are leveraged by other standards, such as htsget.

3.2.8 File Formats

GA4GH standards include the VCF, BAM, and CRAM¹⁶ file formats among others. These ensure that genomic information is consistently represented, and help underpin the bioinformatic analysis tools and APIs. For example, using such consistent file formats allows the implementation of htsget on Crypt4GH encrypted CRAM files, allowing secure federated access to remote genetic data. Additionally the Beacon reference implementation utilises the VCF file format to load data into the back-end database.

3.2.9 Task Execution Service

When data may not leave a certain jurisdiction or compute resource, the analyses need to travel to the data; so called data visitation, and hence the analysis can run on a secure processing environment (SPE) from which the raw data may not leave, to facilitate data analysis there needs to be a way of representing the task or analysis that is interoperable between different locations and compute infrastructure. The Task Execution Service¹⁷ (TES) provides a standardised way of defining such a task. This includes the input files, the containers to execute, the output files, and any required logging or metadata.

3.3 Description of Work

3.3.1 Beacon Reference Implementation

The Beacon standard has been implemented in the Beacon reference implementation¹⁸ including documentation¹⁹ on how to deploy the Beacon, as well as loading data to the Beacon, for example via VCF files for the variants and phenopackets for the phenotypic information.

Two instances of a Beacon V2 were also deployed at CSC, in this case as part of the B1MG PoC as well as the European Genomic Data Infrastructure²⁰ (GDI) Starter Kit, which aim to demonstrate a full user story from synthetic data discovery, through data access request, data access authorisation, to analysis. The B1MG PoC Beacon²¹ has been connected to the development of ELIXIR Beacon Network

¹⁵ <http://samtools.github.io/hts-specs/crypt4gh.pdf>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/samtools/hts-specs>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/ga4gh/task-execution-schemas>

¹⁸ <https://github.com/EGA-archive/beacon2-ri-api>

¹⁹ <https://b2ri-documentation.readthedocs.io/en/latest/beacon-v2-reference-implementation/>

²⁰ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

²¹ <https://b1mg-beacon.rahtiapp.fi/api>

as an example of federated discovery. The ELIXIR Beacon Network supports the LS AAI, and hence allows anonymous, registered, or controlled access queries, again via the GA4GH Passport standard. A list of Beacons deployed is given in Table 1. Additionally the GDI Beacon²² has been connected to the updated version 2 Beacon Network and associated Federated Discovery Portal²³ as described in CINECA deliverable D1.3 “Federated discovery across registry services”²⁴, along with GDI Beacons from Sweden, Belgium, and Luxembourg (as of June 20th 2023).

The BQC19²⁵ Beacon has been deployed for Covid-19 data hosted by Calcul Québec and Compute Canada for the Canadian Centre for Computational Genomics, with 6166 individuals. It is a different implementation²⁶ to the reference implementation, making use of a microservice added to the Bento platform²⁷. This demonstrates the importance of the GA4GH Beacon standard, as different implementations based on different use cases are interoperable.

In Africa, a Beacon has been implemented on the H3Africa²⁸ dataset of high-depth whole genome sequenced genomes, but this Beacon currently conforms to the Beacon version 1 standard - only responding with boolean results.

The range of different implementations, from stand alone implementations, such as the reference implementation, to implementations that are constituent parts of a platform with additional functionality, such as Molgenis or the Bento platform, demonstrates the importance of GA4GH standards allowing interoperability between diverse deployments, datasets, and continents.

3.3.2 Beacon Network

The ELIXIR Beacon Network has been used to link Beacons, and provide federated data discovery services. However, it does not fully implement the Beacon version 2 standard. Hence work has been ongoing to develop a new version of a Beacon Network²⁹ which will fully support the version 2 standard. A development version has been deployed for demonstration³⁰ purposes, which support the full range of Beacon version 2 queries.

3.3.3 WP4 Use case

Working closely with WP4, a demonstrator utilising the expression quantitative trait loci (eQTL) analysis use case has been performed. This use case demonstrated multiple different GA4GH standards to allow a user to discover, access, and then analyse data in a federated context. Discovery was performed using the Beacon v2 standard, via the Reference Implementation described above. Federated analysis could then be performed on the data within different secure processing

²² <https://gdi-demo.sd.csc.fi/beacon/api>

²³ <https://beacon-network-cineca-demo.ega-archive.org/>

²⁴ <https://www.cineca-project.eu/deliverables>

²⁵ <https://bqc19.c3g.calculquebec.ca/api/beacon>

²⁶ https://github.com/bento-platform/bento_beacon

²⁷ <https://github.com/bento-platform>

²⁸ https://beacon.h3abionet.org/h3a_wgs/info

²⁹ <https://gitlab.bsc.es/inb/ga4gh/beacon-network-v2>

³⁰ <https://beacon-network-demo.ega-archive.org/>

environments. For example, at CSC the institutional identity was linked to a LS AAI identity, allowing a user to log into CSC resources using their LS AAI identity. This in turn allows the user to run analyses in compute at CSC, such as the SD Desktop. SD Desktop provides a Secure Processing Environment (SPE) for sensitive data, which has no access to the internet. A user can create an account, and then log in using their LS AAI identity, at which point they can access sensitive data and perform analyses on these data using virtual machines (VMs). The data within SD Desktop is local to CSC, and encrypted at rest using Crypt4GH, being decrypted as it is transferred from the object storage to the user's VM. The data utilised for this use case was UK1³¹ synthetic data, which was originally transferred from the EGA via the htsgget protocol. This is an example of allowing federated computation local to a cohort, which could exist in Europe, Canada, or Africa.

3.3.4 WP5 Use Case

WP5 utilised the B1MG synthetic cancer dataset³² as it included an individual with a breast cancer diagnosis, with a causative mutation added to their genotype. This dataset was accessible from EGA, so the whole data access process was performed, which includes the checking of the data use conditions via the DUO. Once access was granted, the genomic data was streamed out from EGA via the PyEGA3 downloaded, which supports the GA4GH htsgget streaming protocol. The data was streamed directly into a Galaxy³³ instance, which allowed analysis on these data. The Galaxy workflows have been added to the Tools Registry Service (TRS) API, and the Beacon standard has been integrated into Galaxy³⁴.

3.4 Next steps

The WP4 and WP5 use cases within CINECA have utilised the services and standards provided by WP1 for federated Discovery and Querying. However, some of these processes require manual intervention and hence are prime candidates for automation. These services and standards, developed in WP1 and in conjunction with WP2 (LS AAI) and WP3 (minimal metadata model / Data Use Ontology / GECKO) collectively can be built on via other projects, such as EJP-RD³⁵, and the Digital Europe European Genomic Data Infrastructure³⁶ deployment project, as well as the Federated EGA³⁷. Continuing to bring the lessons and requirements from CINECA and associated projects to GA4GH, such as via the CINECA workshop³⁸ at the GA4GH Connect³⁹ meeting, is crucial to ensure the development of a federated genomic data sharing within Europe and worldwide.

³¹ <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001006673>

³² <https://ega-archive.org/datasets/EGAD00001008392>

³³ <https://galaxyproject.org/>

³⁴ <https://galaxyproject.org/news/2023-01-beacon-integration/>

³⁵ <https://www.ejprarediseases.org/>

³⁶ <https://gdi.onemilliongenomes.eu/>

³⁷ <https://ega-archive.org/federated>

³⁸ https://docs.google.com/document/d/15Wk_WoMO8CROA7PfPseCwr6K76nEq6TC/edit

³⁹ <https://broadinstitute.swoogo.com/ga4ghaprilconnect23/>

4. References

Standards

[Beacon Standard](#)

[Phenopacket standard](#)

[GA4GH Passport standard](#)

[GA4GH AAI standard](#)

[Data Use Ontology](#)

[htsget standard](#)

[Crypt4GH standard](#)

[TES standard](#)

Implementations

[Beacon reference implementation](#)

[Beacon Network](#)

5. Abbreviations

AAI	Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure
BBMRI	Biobanking and Biomolecular Resources Research Infrastructure
DAC	Data Access Committee
DUO	Data Use Ontology
EGA	European Genome-phenome Archive
EJP-RD	The European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GDI	European Genomics Data Infrastructure
IDM	Identity Management system
IdP	Identity Provider
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JWT	JSON Web Token
LS AAI	Life Science AAI service, also called LS Login
OIDC	OpenID Connect
REMS	Resource Entitlement Management System
SPE	Secure Processing Environment
TES	Task Execution Service
TRS	Tool Registry Service
VM	Virtual Machine

6. Delivery and schedule

On time

7. Adjustments made

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8. Appendices

Appendix 1

Table 1: List of different Beacon deployments across Europe, Canada, and Africa.

Beacon	Location	Version
BSC Java Beacon 2.0	https://beacons.bsc.es/beacon/v2.0.0/	2
CINECA Synthetic Cohort Europe UK1 Beacon Test	https://ega-archive.org/beacon-apis/cineca/	2
B1MG Beacon Test Record	https://b1mg-beacon.rahtiapp.fi/api	2
GA4GH Approval Beacon Demo	https://ga4gh-approval-beacon.ega-archive.org/api/info/	2
Beacon @ RD-Connect	https://playground.rd-connect.eu/beacon2/api	2
Cafe Variome Beacon v2	https://beaconv2.cafevariome.org/	2
Progenetix Cancer Genomics Beacon+	https://progenetix.org/beacon/	2
SweFreq	https://swefreq.nbis.se/dataset/SweGen/beacon	1
European Variation Archive - EBI GA4GH Beacon	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/eva/?GA4GH	1
ValidSpliceMut	https://validsplicemut.cytognomix.com/	
MOLGENIS Beacon v2	https://vkgl-emx2.molgeniscloud.org/api/beacon/info	2
CanDig Beacon	https://cineca.bento.c3g.calculquebec.ca/api/beacon/	2

Appendix 2

Standard	Specification	Documentation
Beacon	GitHub - ga4gh-beacon/specification	https://docs.genomebeacons.org/
Phenopackets	Repository for the GA4GH phenopacket schema	https://phenopacket-schema.readthedocs.io/en/latest/
Passports	GA4GH Passport	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2021.100030
GA4GH AAI	AAI OIDC Profile GA4GH Data Security	https://ga4gh.github.io/data-security/aai-faq
DUO	GitHub - EBISPO/DOU: Ontology for consent codes and data use requirements	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.xgen.2021.100028
htsget	htsget protocol	https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/bty492
Crypt4GH	GA4GH File Encryption Standard	https://doi.org/10.1093/bioinformatics/btab087
TES	GitHub - ga4gh/task-execution-schemas	https://ga4gh.github.io/task-execution-schemas/docs/
Implementation		
Beacon	GitHub - EGA-archive/beacon2-ri-api: Beacon v2 Reference Implementation (API)	
Beacon Network	https://gitlab.bsc.es/inb/ga4gh/beacon-network-v2	
LS AAI	https://lifescience-ri.eu/ls-login/	

